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Electrical System Audit of a University Laboratory

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Abstract

An electrical system audit is important in every building or dwelling to ensure the safety of the occupants. The audit was conducted following the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating, and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) level 2 standard. In this study where the locale is a university laboratory, results found that there is a thermal anomaly in the main distribution panels, which is an indication of a loose connection or possible overload and leads to technical system loss, loss of energy and cause a fire in the long run. There are also multiple cable splices going to the distribution panel, which is a violation of the electrical code. The lighting in the area does not meet the required illumination for laboratory safety. Moreover live bus bars were exposed on the distribution panel.

Keywords: illumination; hot spot; safety; systems loss; electrical panels

1. Introduction

Many elements have affected the environment, and have directly affected people. Well-designed environments make people happy, energize and vice versa. These elements start with building structure and shape, and are complete with a color, light, electrical system, outside viewing, and furnish. Sometimes, the influence of light through a good electrical system in the environment is much more than other elements. Understanding the relationship between light, good electrical systems, and the environment can help designers or architects to improve interior designs for better performance (Samani S., 2011). Electrical system design has become increasingly significant to electrical designers and engineers. With the

advent of high energy costs, designers have needed to become more aware of electrical systems. In an electric utility system, loss means the difference between the amounts of sent energy from a station and the building amount to customers in an electrical system. Invariably, laboratories, commercial buildings, schools, and households' electrical distribution systems are no exception on it.

In these important aspects of an electrical distribution system, electrical power, and energy lost when transmitted to customers can represent a significant expense to Cebu Technological University – Hitachi Robotics and Metrology Laboratory which is our locale of the study. Reducing electrical losses through the enhancement of the present installation will limit the associated economic burden. For Cebu Technological University – Hitachi Robotics and Metrology Laboratory, it is difficult to state in general terms what savings might achieve by implementing economically justifiable measures to reduce electrical system deficiencies. It has existing systems that already consist of low-loss components and configuration, but those old lines and equipment may discover numerous possibilities to achieve losses. In the process of eliminating electrical system deficiencies, this study proposes a defect identification methodology using Plan – Do – Check – Act and determined which component contributes greatly to the electrical system, therefore this study. The electrical grid that spans continents is typically made up of a few large networks. Within those networks, all hundreds of thousands of electricity flow freely among lines and distribution cables of many electrical systems following Kirchhoff's Law (IEEE Spectrum, Jul. 2003).

Bringing power from generation delivery points to the customers and transforming the same to lower voltage, electricity is dissipated or lost. The transmission of electricity results in some loss of electrical energy even in the most efficient systems

(IEEE Spectrum, Jan. 2004). In the Philippines, the extent to which losses occur due to electrical installation deficiencies in any electrical distribution system is measured by the value called efficiency. The lost electrical energy is bought by the utility company and resold to the customer, this unpaid energy results in major operating costs. The components of cost are usually combined into a single figure either in terms of cents per kilowatt-hour of total energy loss or the amount per kilowatt-hour of peak loss. Expressing losses in terms of money per kilowatt is called capitalized cost of losses and in some advantages in that, it shows directly the amount of money that could be economically spent to save 1kw of losses (Hazan, 1982).

Department of Energy estimates that at least 154 TWh will be needed in the next decade as baseline consumption for end-use lighting. In this case, it is very important for Cebu Technological University – Hitachi Laboratory to determine the optimal levels of illumination requirements to save energy.

2. Research methodology

The researcher used acausal-the comparative research method. This study sought to determine particular, actual situations as they are. It involved an assessment of the electrical system of Cebu Technological University – Hitachi Robotics and Metrology Laboratory, analysis of data gathered, and interpretation of conditions that exist under the American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers (ASHRAE) level 2 standard.

This study aims to assess the electrical system of Cebu Technological University – Hitachi Robotics and Metrology Laboratory, determine design deficiencies, and present corrective actions. Surveys are administered through actual site inspection, interviews, and functional group discussions of the administrators involved. The ocular inspection had been conducted to check the total connected load,

evaluation through the use of a thermal imager and other electrical analyzing instruments to circuit breakers, circuit home runs, and electrical panels, grounding system protection, illumination, and observed violation to existing standards. Field interviews focusing on the practices, equipment failure incidents due to low or high voltage, breaker failure, and other related useful data had been conducted.

The data gathered through interviews and ocular inspections and from results through the use of electrical analyzing equipment were tallied and treated statistically. Recommendations, analysis, interpretation of data, and recommendations are patterned to a commonly used tool, the Plan – Do – Check – Act cycle. Figure 1. shows the research flow diagram using the PDCA cycle.

Figure 1. Flow of the study.

3. Results and discussions

Cebu Technological University – Hitachi Robotics & Metrology Laboratory is subdivided into four rooms, these are Mechatronics Laboratory No. 4, Mechatronics Laboratory No. 3, Lapping Area, and Office of the Dean. Mechatronics Laboratory No. 4 has a total area of 72.6 square meters, Mechatronics Laboratory No. 3 with a total area of 43.45 square meters, Lapping Area with 100.04 square meters, and Office of the Dean with a total area of 15.82 square meters. Finished floor level to ceiling has a total height of 3.70 meters while work plane to ceiling has a total height of 2.90 meters (measured from the top

of the laboratory table to ceiling reinforced concrete slab).

Nine (9) identified locations were tested using an Illumination meter to test current illumination in each room at CTU – Hitachi Robotics and Metrology Laboratory, for the data collection. Figure 2 shows an estimated location where the test was conducted, the position of the instrument is above the work plane. The work plane is an estimated distance from the finished floor level to the tabletop where most of the equipment is positioned and of the same level. Table 1. shows the tabulated result taken at a selected significant location/room in comparison to the Occupational Health and Safety Standard as

amended by the Department of Labor and Employment which states that: “A minimum of 300 lux (30-foot candles) shall be provided where close discrimination of details is essential”.

Figure 2. Measured illumination taken at different point at CTU – Hitachi Robotics & Metrology Laboratory.

Table 1. Tabular illumination in Lux using illumination meter.

Point(s)/Location	Measured Illumination (Lux)	Standard Illumination (Lux)
Mechatronics Laboratory # 3		
1	112	300
2	134	300
3	225	300
4	60	300
5	86	300
6	45	300
7	90	300
8	48	300
9	114	300
Mechatronics Laboratory # 4		
1	56	300
2	237	300
3	40	300
4	95	300
5	61	300
6	59	300
7	207	300
8	194	300

Point(s)/Location	Measured Illumination (Lux)	Standard Illumination (Lux)
9	30	300
Office/Lapping Area		
1	134	300
2	60	300
3	103	300
4	98	300
5	227	300
6	23	300
7	285	300
8	226	300
9	178	300

The scatter graph in Figure 3. shows that there is a strong positive relationship between Mechatronics Laboratory No. 4 and the Lapping/Office area with the standard illumination for laboratories. These are indicated by the red and green regression line going up while strong negative relationship for data measured at the Mechatronics Laboratory No. 3 concerning standard illumination for laboratories as

indicated by the black regression line going down. Data also show that no single point of reference in the three rooms being measured meets the 300 lux (30-foot candles) illumination requirement based on the standard. Overall these laboratories did not meet the required illumination standard for laboratories. The scatter plot indicates uneven illumination.

Figure 3. Scatter plot result on measured illumination vs. standard data illumination for Hitachi Robotics & Metrology Laboratory.

Cebu Technological University's main transformers are oil-immersed transformers located on the front of the building mounted in a transformer pad. The total

installed capacity is 750 kVA, composed of 3 – 250 kVA individual transformers interconnected together in a wye-delta configuration. The primary voltage

rating is 23,000 volts (23kV) and the secondary is 240 volts in a line-to-line configuration. The transformer location is too close to a building without space separation. The National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) 70 also known as National Electrical Code Handbook, 2002 Edition under article 450.27 requires that combustible materials, combustible buildings, and parts of the buildings shall be safeguarded from fires originating in an oil-immersed transformer installed to or adjacent to a building. In case the transformer installation presents a fire hazard, one or more of the following safeguards shall be applied according to the degree of hazard

Figure 4. Thermal scanning and actual images of CTU 3 x 250kVA transformer

involved. These are space separation, fire-resistant barriers, automatic fire suppression systems, or an enclosure.

Figure 4. shows the thermal scanning images using Fluke Ti25 Thermal Imager. A temperature reading has an average of 40.2 degrees Celsius with a maximum of 45.5 degrees Celsius which appears to be normal. The object distance is 1.5 meters from the equipment taken at 2:20 in the afternoon; the weather is dry with an ambient temperature of 29 to 30 degree Celsius.

Four cables per phase of 250 square millimeters, THHN used as main conductors from the transformer to the main distribution panel. It was also observed that there are splices in between the transformer and 1,800 amperes main circuit breakers line side of the main distribution panel. The live bus bars in the panel board are exposed to dust accumulation. Figure 5. shows splices between two terminals. The National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) 70 also known as National Electrical Code Handbook, 2002 Edition under article 300.13(A) states that splices or taps are prohibited within raceways unless the raceway is equipped with a hinged or removable cover.

Figure 5. Cable splices from transformer towards main distribution panel

The main distribution panel is located inside the building with 1800 amperes, three-phase, and 240 volts main with four branches, these are 600 amperes, three-phase, 2 by 100 square millimeters in diameter THHN cable for College of Education; 400 amperes, three-phase, 2 by 100 square millimeters in diameter THHN cable for Administration Building; 400 amperes, three-phase, 1 by 100 square millimeters in diameter THHN cable for College of Technology Building and 125 amperes, three-phase intended as spare. It was observed that the bus bars of the main distribution panel are exposed and the entrance door has no restriction. Hotspots were also found on the load and line side of the breakers and a potential sign of a loose connection.

Figure 6. Hot spot at 400 Amperes supplying College of Technology

Figure 6. shows the thermal scanning images using Fluke Ti25 Thermal Imager. Temperature reading has a maximum of 85.8 degrees Celsius; object distance is 1.5 meters from the equipment taken 2:30 in the afternoon, weather is dry with an ambient temperature of 29 to 30 degree Celsius. Results show that there is t hot spot in the component and a sign of loose contact.

4. Summary and conclusions

Based on the results of the study, it was found that there is a hot spot in the main distribution panel which is an indication of loose contact and an overload system. Hot spot contributes to technical systems loss. There were no available barriers between the transformer and the main building which is a safety concern. Unenclosed multiple cable splices going to the main distribution panel which is a violation of the electrical code. Present illumination did not meet the Occupational Safety and Health Standard which requires a minimum of 300 lux for laboratory application. There are also exposed/unsecured live bus bars at the main distribution panel. The distribution panel/feeder located at the Hitachi Robotics and Metrology Laboratory is enclosed with a plyboard, a highly combustible material. Without a permanent power source tapping point for most of the laboratory equipment and no available 208Vac, 3 phases for two laboratory equipment located at Mechatronics Laboratory No. 3. Lastly, breakers used as overcurrent protection devices for laboratory equipment did not meet the ampere – interrupting requirements as per equipment manufacturer specifications.

With all of these findings, the institution must revisit/strengthen its maintenance program, and initiate immediate corrective measures, particularly on high-risk issues like a loose connection, poor

illumination, unenclosed multiple splicing, safety barriers, unsecured live bus bars and removal of combustible materials within the power centers. For the equipment that needs a specialized supply of 208 Vac, this can be addressed by a transformer, breakers also can be replaced following machine/load ampere-interrupting capacity requirements.

Author contributions

Conceptualization [E.C.]; methodology [M.C.]; software [E.C.]; validation [M.C.]; formal analysis

[E.C.]; investigation [E.C.]; resources [E.C.]; data curation [E.C.]; writing—original draft preparation [M.C.]; writing—review and editing [M.C.]; visualization [E.C.]; supervision (E.C.); project administration [E.C.]; funding acquisition [M.C.]

All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Conflict of interest

The authors declares no conflict of interest.

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